

Extraction of Anthocyanin from *Hibiscus* flower and its complexation with Metal

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Abstract:

The demand for safe and eco-friendly natural colourants has risen, leading to a growing interest in colors present in different flowers and vegetables. Flowers are of great interest as massive amount of flowers are wasted during Pooja and worshipping places like temples etc. Different flowers have different coloring moieties but colors like red and green are always in great demand. This factor led to study colors present in *Hibiscus* flower which not only have a vibrant red hue but also possess medicinal properties too.

In this study, the focus is on extracting natural colour from red flower and fruit viz. *Hibiscus* (*Hibiscus rosasinensis*) and then studies will be carried out to enhancing its shelf life by complexation with inorganic salts along with stability study of red pigment i.e. anthocyanin present in them through different techniques. The study will offer valuable insights into the extraction of anthocyanin and its subsequent complexation with inorganic salts to enhance stability that opens opportunities for the development of functional food and beverage having stable natural color replacing their synthetic counterparts.

Keywords: Color, Anthocyanin, Inorganic salts, Complexation, stable natural color

1. Introduction

In the nineteenth century, when chemistry was in its infancy, chemists proposed that the colour produced by dyes may be due to the interaction of light with the specific moieties present in the chemical structures of molecules. The pigments found in different parts of the plants such as anthocyanins, betalains, carotenoids, annatto etc. can be used to impart different colours in foods.

In recent years, interest in food quality has increased. Consumers are increasingly becoming aware about the correlation between nutrition and health. Thus, many consumers are opting

for foods that contain bioactive ingredients, which have health-promoting properties (Nyau 2014). Vegetables and fruits have high amounts of antioxidant compounds that are considered bioactive ingredients. Different chemical compounds present in vegetables, fruits, and flowers have antioxidant properties. Some of these compounds belong to the group of anthocyanins, which are not only antioxidant compounds, but are also natural colorants (with aglycones of anthocyanins being the most common plant pigments). During the past 50 years, an industry focusing on natural food colors has developed, with the focus on providing natural, safe and stable food colors. Natural food colors originate from a wide range of sources like vegetables, fruits, spices, algae and/or other edible natural sources. They offer a wide spectrum of colors and impart color when added to food or drink (Association 2023). Natural food colors are preparations obtained from foods and other edible natural source materials obtained by physical and/or chemical extraction resulting in a selective extraction of the pigments relative to the nutritive or aromatic constituents. Food coloring is used both in commercial food production and in domestic cooking. Anthocyanins are naturally occurring pigments belonging to the group of flavonoids, a subclass of the polyphenol family containing a flavylium cation (Martín, Navas et al. 2017). Anthocyanins are secondary plant metabolites and are synthesized in almost all higher order plants (Nyau 2014). They are water soluble pigments responsible for the attractive red, purple and blue colors of many flowers, fruits and vegetables. They are sensitive to pH change, being reddest in strongly acidic conditions and become bluer as the pH rises and used in drinks, jams and sugar confectionery (Association 2023). These are focus of much attention these days due to their vibrant colours and immunity-boosting and health-promoting affects mainly in ameliorating various cholesterol-related and oxidation-induced diseases. All of these mentioned functions, effects and activities of anthocyanins are due to their unique structure. Anthocyanins being water-soluble pigments have high hydrogen bonding capacity. The OH groups on their sugar moieties, possible acyl groups and anthocyanidin imparts them hydrophilic characteristics. Anthocyanins are responsible for the red, purple, and blue colours found in fruits, vegetables, and flowers. There are several types of anthocyanins, such as delphinidin, cyanidin, pelargonidin, petunidin, and malvidin, each contributing to specific shades of colour (Zhang, Li et al. 2022).

Figure1:Structure of anthocyanin R₃ = sugar and anthocyanidins R₃ = H (Tena, Martín et al. 2020)

The interest in anthocyanins can be attributed to the fact that they can be used as natural coloring agents rather than as synthetic coloring agents (Albuquerque, Pinela et al. 2020),(Fernandes, Pereira et al. 2019),(Ngamwonglumlert, Devahastin et al. 2017). Anthocyanins have attractive colors, ranging from red to purple, and their use as food coloring agents has been authorized under code E163 by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) (Albuquerque, Pinela et al. 2020), (Additives and Food 2013). This has expanded the use of these natural coloring agents at the industrial level; they can be included in the food industry because they are innocuous and safe molecules. Moreover, anthocyanins have gained attention due to their potential health benefits, e.g., (i) anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-diabetic, and anti-cancer properties; (ii) preventing cardiovascular diseases, neurological disorders, obesity, and for eye health; (iii) improving the gut microbiome; and (iv) decreasing H₂O₂induced cell apoptosis of the human normal liver cell (LO2 cell) line (Hair, Sakaki et al. 2021),(Kumar, Srivastav et al. 2021),(Gao, Ji et al. 2021). Thus, anthocyanins provide excellent added value to foods due to their dual nature as coloring agents and antioxidants,

with beneficial effects on health. Therefore, they are determining factors in the quality and value of fruits and vegetables, and in processed food derived from those. In addition, they can be widely used in the food and cosmetics industries.

The stability of anthocyanins can be influenced by factors like pH, temperature, light exposure, oxygen, metal ions, and sugar content. Anthocyanins change colour based on pH levels, appearing red in acidic conditions and blue or green in alkaline conditions. High temperatures and exposure to UV light can degrade anthocyanins, resulting in colour loss. Additionally, oxidation and the presence of metal ions can affect the stability of anthocyanins. To enhance their stability in food applications, adjusting pH levels, controlling temperature and light exposure, and using stabilizing agents like antioxidants or chelating agents are common strategies.

At present, expensive raw materials and production technologies make the extraction of natural anthocyanins relatively expensive (Jezek, Zörb et al. 2018), (Moirangthem, Ramakrishna et al. 2021). For this reason, new sources of anthocyanins which are easily available locally are being studied, in order to extract these compounds at lower costs. *Hibiscus rosasinensis* (China rose) is used as anthocyanin source in this study and this has been tried to complex with copper and alum to increase their stability and their stability/quality has been checked by spectroscopic methods.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

2.1.1 Plant material

Hibiscus rosasinensis flowers were procured from the local market, Kanpur, India and they were kept in cold (20°C) and dark storage until processed (the shelf life was found to be for more than a month).

2.1.2 Chemicals and Glassware

All the chemicals (Methanol, copper sulphate, Alum etc.) were procured from S D Fine chemicals in Kanpur are of analytical grade. All the glassware used is of Borosil make.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Moisture Content Analysis

Hibiscus flowers were taken to determine the moisture content. The sample (100 gm of flowers) was kept in an oven at 100°C for 5 to 6 hrs and then weighed. The procedure was repeated three times to get a constant weight. Percentage moisture was calculate with the help of following equation –

$$\text{Moisture content} = (\text{wet wt.} - \text{dry wt.} / \text{wet wt.}) * 100$$

2.2.2 Anthocyanin extraction

Anthocyanin extraction was carried out by acidic methanol. The green corolla part of *Hibiscus* flowers was removed and petals were cut into small pieces and anthocyanin was extracted from flowers with 0.1% HCl (v/v) in methanol for 2 to 3 hrs at room temperature, in darkness without heating or stirring. The mixture was filtered on a Buchner funnel and the remaining solids were washed with 0.1% HCl in methanol until a clear solution was obtained (Longo, Scardino et al. 2007). For complete recovery of Colorant/anthocyanin, flower material with acidified methanol was heated a little in the end. The combined filtrates were little concentrated and used for metal complexation and spectroscopic analysis.

2.2.3 Quantification of Anthocyanin

Anthocyanin so extracted was dried in preweighed beaker at 50°C in an oven and weighed after drying. The procedure was repeated three times to get a constant weight. This analysis will give a rough estimate of the extracted anthocyanin from *Hibiscus* flowers.

2.2.4 Metal Chelation of Anthocyanin

For chelating metal entities to Anthocyanin, inorganic salts solutions were prepared in deionized water. 100ppm solutions of Alum and copper sulphate were prepared by dissolving accurate quantity (100mg of salt in 100 ml of DI water) of salt in DI water. After salt solution preparation, it was stabilised (kept for a while) and then mixed with anthocyanin solution and kept in dark for 1 hrs. after thorough mixing.

2.2.5 Spectroscopic analysis of color extracts

UV-Visible analysis of intrinsic anthocyanin extract of *Hibiscus* was carried out. The presence of colorant and metal complexes was also checked by spectroscopic analysis of the each extract. The UV VIS analysis was carried out on UV VIS 1800 Shimadzu model spectrophotometer at a resolution of 1 nm.

IR analysis was also carried out of both anthocyanin (*Hibiscus*) as well as metal complexes of anthocyanin on Spectrum Two (ATR) Model of Perkin Elmer.

3. Results and Discussion:

The food industry is currently looking for new sources of bioactive compounds, such as anthocyanins, to meet consumer demands. Anthocyanins are considered high added-value compounds due to their sensory qualities, colors, and nutritional properties; they are considered bioactive ingredients. Anthocyanin extraction and their stability are of great concern. Thus their extraction with mild agent and their stabilising through metal chelation has been tried. A very low concentration of Copper sulphate and Alum are used to complex extracted anthocyanin from *Hibiscus* flowers.

Moisture Content of Flowers

Moisture content of *Hibiscus* flowers was found to be 89.36% (100 gm fresh flowers).

Role of Solvent

Considering the law that “like dissolves like”, the solvents commonly used to extract anthocyanins are: methanol, ethanol, water, acetone, or mixtures thereof. Acid solutions are often added to these solvents to help stabilize the flavylium cation, which is stable in highly acidic conditions (pH ~ 3). To achieve this, mild acid is used. In view of the polar structure of the anthocyanins, the addition of water to the solvent mixture can improve the extractive yield. Although all the above solvents are good but methanol was found to be most efficient solvent for this kind of extraction. In drying anthocyanin, water dried out and anthocyanin remains in the system at low temperature (40-55°C). These types of extractions are currently the most widely used in the industry, particularly in natural dye industries, likely because these extraction methods have low instrumentation costs (Tena and Asuero 2022).

Anthocyanin yield

Anthocyanin yield was determined by drying extracted colorant and getting stable weight. Approximate anthocyanin yield in *Hibiscus* flower was found to be 1.02% extracted on 100 gm flowers.

Metal Chelation and Spectroscopic Analysis

The effect of Metal chelation on extracted anthocyanin of *Hibiscus* was observed with spectroscopic analysis. Their spectra are observed with very sharp peaks of Anthocyanin in intrinsic extract and changes in UV region after metal addition. These peaks range from 520nm

to 550nm before and after metal addition (Fig. 3-5). The addition of Copper Sulphate and alum increased conjugation as can be observed with increase absorbance and multiple peaks in UV region. The more the conjugation more stable will be the molecule. Visible region peak remain at almost same wavelength in all metal complexed anthocyanin samples. These metal entities obviously may/will increase shelf life of Anthocyanin. The amount of metal entity can be calculated by stoichiometric formulae, which can also provide the exact quantity of metal moiety attached to anthocyanin molecule present in *Hibiscus* which is cyanidin-3-sophoroside (Nakamura, Hidaka et al. 1990). Anthocyanin-metal complex constitutes a viable alternative for color stabilization, particularly if the metals involved do not imply a risk for the environmental pollution. One of the main characteristics of anthocyanins and anthocyanidins with *o*-dihydroxyl groups in the B ring (Cyanidin, Delphinidin, Petunidin) is their ability to form metal-anthocyanin complexes (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Possible Metal chelation in Anthocyanin (M = Metal) (Celli, Selig et al. 2018)

Some studies about the color stability in plants, suggest that the blue colors are due to a complexation between anthocyanin and some metals such as Al, Fe, Cu and Sn (Moncada, Moura et al. 2003). It was found that anthocyanin dye in strawberry, raspberry, and cherry preserves could be stabilized by the addition of alum as well as stannous and stannic chloride salts (Vankar and Shukla 2011). Some metals, such as Iron and Aluminium form stable deeply colored coordination complexes with anthocyanins that bear ortho-dihydroxyphenyl structure

on the B-ring (Starr and Francis 1973). Anthocyanin extract from *Hibiscus* flower formed a deep red color complex in this study. As far as IR spectra are concerned, almost all spectra shown same peaks and thus constitutionally molecule remains the same (Fig. 6-8). Every IR spectra has shown intense peaks at 3500 (hydroxyl group) and at 1710 cm (carbonyl group) and that of metal chelated anthocyanin has less intense peaks at these wavelengths which may be due to complexation of O-hydroxycarbonyl moiety of the anthocyanin molecules (Figure 6, 7, 8). It is also observed that one small hump also generate at about 890 cm^{-1} in these spectra suggesting sugar moiety change.

Figure 3: Visible spectra of *Hibiscus* anthocyanin

Figure 4: Visible spectra of *Hibiscus* anthocyanin complexed with CuSO_4

Figure 5: Visible spectra of *Hibiscus* anthocyanin complexed with Alum

Figure 6: IR of *Hibiscus* anthocyanin

Figure 7: IR of *Hibiscus* anthocyanin complexed with CuSO₄

Figure 8: IR of *Hibiscus* anthocyanin complexed with Alum

Anthocyanins in fruits and vegetables are important sources of natural colorants. Copigmentation with metal ions is a viable mechanism to impart the color and improve the stability of anthocyanins from plant and fruit extracts (Ratanapoompinyo, Nguyen et al. 2017). The chelation of metal ions by anthocyanins was reported to stabilize the quinonoidal base and protect the anthocyanin molecule from nucleophilic attack (Yoshida, Mori et al. 2009). This

color stabilization may be useful as heat used while cooking may deteriorate color used in food recipe.

4. Conclusions:

The color of a food will influence not only the perception of flavour, but also that of appearance and quality. It is also important not to underestimate aesthetic value. The best food with a perfect balance of nutrients is useless if it is not consumed. Consequently, food needs to be attractive. If the color used in food is of natural origin then its very virtuous both aesthetically as well as nutritionally. Anthocyanin extraction and increasing its shelf life through metal chelation can be very helpful step in using flower in coloring food material like jams, jellies and base for cakes as the above study proved. These flowers are available in abundance. Their use for extraction of anthocyanin can be easily achieved and metal chelation can further give stability to anthocyanin without hampering its quality as shown by spectral analysis. *Hibiscus* extract, already used to give color and flavour to beverages and many other food items whereas utilization of anthocyanin extract from *Hibiscus* flowers is new in this foray. As metal complexation provide stability and deep color profile, this flower can successfully be used as economic food dye since complexed anthocyanin has better dye ability. Large scale extraction can be beneficial step in this regard. Thus development of economically viable industrial extraction methods for mass extraction is need of the hour. This will be more effective if cheap technology and easy industrial installation will go hand in hand. Thus after easy extraction of anthocyanin, technology and cost should be a key focus in future research to make the whole food coloring industry bio-sustainable.

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